

Analysing Shooting Incidents in New York Using Spatial Regression Techniques

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Summary

Spatial regression techniques usually applied to area data are here adapted to work with network data - in this case road sections. An example is given exploring spatial patterns in shooting incidents in a neighbourhood of New York City, making use of open data. Risks of a shooting occurring are modeled using both Poisson and negative binomial distributions, and compared using an Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) approach - which suggests that the negative binomial model (in which events tend to cluster) is more plausible than the Poisson.

KEYWORDS: Gun Crime, Open Data, Spatial Regression, Network Data, Markov Random Field

1 Introduction

There are many examples of spatial statistical techniques applied to area and point data, but possibly fewer applied to line data, such as road networks. However there is at least one straight-forward way to adapt methods applied to zonal data that make use of adjacencies between zones. This is useful when the phenomenon under investigation has an underlying geography relating to roads and/or footpaths. Proximity of events here is perhaps more meaningfully defined when they take place on the same street, or adjacent streets, rather than by Euclidean distance. Two events could be close in terms of ‘crow-fly’ distance, but actually be on opposite sides of a river (with no nearby bridge) for example.

In this situation, spatially referencing events by assigning them to road sections, and noting the connectivity of these sections offers a practical way forward. The spatial structure of these road sections may then be encapsulated by noting which road sections meet and end points and junction points. This functions in the same way as an adjacency matrix does in area based models of spatial autocorrelation. As an example, in Figure 1 there are six road sections, and each of the blue ones is adjacent to the ‘Main’ red one. Also the three blue segments in the north east are mutually adjacent, as are the three blue ones in the south west.

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Figure 1: Adjacency on a street network.

This method will be demonstrated here using data relating to historic shooting incident data from NYC OpenData (2022) - a website managed by the Open Data Team at the NYC Office of Technology and Innovation (OTI) to provide open data relating to New York City. The analysis will be based on identifying spatial trends in the incidents by modelling the intensity of these trends via a Markov Random Field (MRF) defined on the street network of the study area (Haran, 2011). In the following sections the data and the analytical approach will be discussed, and the results of a preliminary analysis will be presented.

2 Data Used

As mentioned earlier the data here refers to historical shooting incidents in New York City. The NYC OpenData web site is a portal for a number of spatial data sets including three downloaded and used here, described briefly in Table 1 :

Table 1: Data sets from NYC OpenData

Data Set (geojson file)	Brief Description
NYC Street Centerline (CSCL).geojson	Street Centerlines
Community Districts (Water Areas Included).geojson	District Boundaries
NYPD Shooting Incident Data (Historic)_20240119.geojson	Shooting Incidents

Each of the files is in `geojson` format - the shootings are point data, and contain a number of attributes relating to the date and time of the shootings (they span from 2006 to the present), as well as other characteristics such as the victim and perpetrator’s age group (if known). The street centerlines also contain several attributes for each street section - including the street’s name (more than one section can make up the entire street), its length and width and its direction of travel (for one-way streets). This data set can be used to derive the adjacencies between sections, as well as for mapping purposes. Finally, the districts file is a set of boundaries for community areas. For this study, district 304, a neighbourhood in Brooklyn, is used. In the time span of the shootings data, this area saw 512 events. The streets and the incidents are shown in Figure 2, which also adds an OpenStreetmap backdrop (OpenStreetMap, 2024) - this backdrop is also applied in other maps in this paper.

Figure 2: Locations of Shooting Incidents.

Using the `st_join` function in the `sf` package in R, with the join matching function being set as `st_nearest_feature` it is possible to ‘snap’ each shooting incident to its nearest road section. Incidents are then tallied by road section to give a new line-based `sf` object where road sections are now tagged with the number of shooting incidents occurring there.

3 Analytical Methods

The aim of the model here is to predict the number of incidents for each road section. One important thing to note is that street sections vary in length, so that even in the situation where there is no variation in risk, longer streets would be expected to see more events. For that reason, the concept of *risk density* in terms of crimes per metre of road is important here. This is the quantity that we may expect to exhibit autocorrelation. If we assume that certain street sections have a higher risk of incidence, we may reasonably expect that other sections close to them in the network have similar risks - essentially Tobler’s first law of geography applied on a network. Finally, since we are modelling counts as the final outcome, an appropriate probability distribution such as Poisson or Negative Binomial should be used. In the first instance, a Poisson model will be adopted. If n_i is the number of events occurring in road section i , r_i is the risk density in section i and l_i is the length of section i , and finally $\lambda_i = \log(r_i)$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} n_i &\sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_i) \\ \text{where} & \\ \log \mu_i &= \lambda_i + \log(l_i) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

To encapsulate spatial autocorrelation the vector of all λ_i ’s is assumed to be generated by a Markov random field - in particular an Intrinsic Conditional Autoregressive (ICAR) field (Besag & Koopman, 1995). This is defined in terms of the conditional distribution of each λ_i given the values of its adjacent neighbours, as in Equation 2 below:

$$\lambda_i \sim N \left(\frac{\sum_j \lambda_j}{A_i}, \sigma^2 \right) \tag{2}$$

where j indexes the set of road sections adjacent to i and A_i is the number of road sections in that set. Essentially given the λ values of the neighbours of section i , the mean value of λ_i is the mean of these. The value of σ^2 then controls the ‘smoothness’ of the process, as it describes how likely any λ_i is likely to stray from this mean value. The task of model calibration here is to estimate the values of the λ_i ’s and σ^2 given the data $\{n_1 \dots n_N\}$ and adjacency information. Such models may be calibrated using the `gam` function in the `mgcv` library in R.

3.1 Preliminary Results

The Poisson-ICAR model was fitted to the count data for road sections. The results are shown in Figure 3. The results look similar to a crime hotspot map (Eck et al., 2005), although some risks

appear to be raised along the direction of streets in a fairly linear way, unlike the usual circular kinds of hotspot see for example the north west corner.

Figure 3: Risk Density Map for Poisson/ICAR Model.

3.2 Alternative Models

An advantage of this approach over conventional hot-spot mapping is that as well as a mapping tool, a probabilistic data model is also provided via equations Equation 1 and Equation 2 - and like other such models, tools for goodness-of-fit and comparison of models can be used. For example, one could exchange in Poisson distribution in Equation 2 for a Negative Binomial. The λ_i 's are still modelled as an ICAR process. The interpretation of this is that the λ_i map (such as in Figure 3) still gives a map of risk density - but if an event is triggered it is more likely to result in a cluster of shootings. In the Poisson model events are independent. Such a model is fitted in Figure 4.

The mapped pattern is similar to that seen in Figure 3, but the hotspot just south of Myrtle Avenue is less intense, suggesting that possibly more clustered events are occurring here.

As mentioned above, in this framework there is also the possibility to compare and assess different models. One way that this can be done is through the use of Akaike information criterion (AIC) - or the alternative Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). This is shown in Table 2. The Baseline model uses a Poisson distribution with a constant λ_i suggesting no spatial variability. Although these quantities do not have identical interpretations both clearly indicate the the best model is the Negative Binomial.

Figure 4: Risk Density Map for Negative Binomial/ICAR Model.

Table 2: Comparison of Models via AIC and BIC - lower values are ‘better’

Model	AIC	BIC
Baseline	2185	2190
Poisson	1858	2037
Negative Binomial	1585	1734

4 Conclusion

The method outlined here demonstrates how street network data may be used in spatial regression models with an alternative version of adjacency. When applied to crime data this provides a model-based variant on hotspot mapping that enables hypotheses relating to spatial processes to be compared and explored.

Although not demonstrated here, the regression modelling aspect of the approach also allows further explanatory variable to be incorporated. For example hypotheses as to whether the age of the perpetrator of the victim had effects on the risk map could be investigated by comparing models fitting different ICAR processes to subgroups of the data to ones that fitted a single process to the entire data.

Finally, although streets were used here for the network data, this could also be applied to similarly structured data - for example pipelines with pipe breakages as an event - or in other applications using road sections, such as the analysis of road traffic accidents.

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Biographies

Chris Brunsdon is Professor of Geocomputation and Director of the National Centre for Geocomputation at the National University of Ireland, Maynooth.

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